

Recursive Decomposition of Factorials via the Consecutive Summation Notation n_+ and the Derivation of a Generalized Formula

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$$3! = 3_+ = 6$$

$$n! = \frac{(n+2)!}{2(n+1)_+}$$

$$3! = \frac{5!}{2 \times 4_+} = 3_+$$

$$5! = \frac{7!}{2 \times 6_+} = 2 \times 3_+ \times 4_+$$

$$7! = \frac{9!}{2 \times 8_+} = 2^2 \times 3_+ \times 4_+ \times 6_+$$

$$9! = \frac{11!}{2 \times 10_+} = 2^3 \times 3_+ \times 4_+ \times 6_+ \times 8_+$$

$$\therefore (2k+1)! = 2^{k-1} \times \prod_{i=2}^k (2i)_+ \times 3_+$$

$$4! = \frac{6!}{2 \times 5_+} = 2^2 \times 3_+$$

$$6! = \frac{8!}{2 \times 7_+} = 2^3 \times 3_+ \times 5_+$$

$$8! = \frac{10!}{2 \times 9_+} = 2^4 \times 3_+ \times 5_+ \times 7_+$$

$$10! = \frac{12!}{2 \times 11_+} = 2^5 \times 3_+ \times 5_+ \times 7_+ \times 9_+$$

$$\therefore (2k)! = 2^k \times \prod_{i=2}^k (2i - 1)_+$$

Starting from the relationship $3! = 3_+$, this paper reformulates the factorial ($n!$) as a combination of lower-order consecutive summations (n_+) and powers of two.

By recursively applying the identity $n! = \frac{(n+2)!}{2(n+1)_+}$, we derive the sequential patterns of n_+ terms inherent in both odd $2k+1$ and even $2k$ factorials, ultimately establishing them as a general formula.

Reference

Kim(2026). A Study on the Reconstruction and Correlation of Factorials Through the Definition of Basic Arithmetic Operations. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19960864>